

Effects of EMS on some characters of selected M₂ plants, Chinsurah, India.

Selection	Duration (d)	Height (cm)	Panicle no.	Panicle length (cm)	Grain size		Grain shape (L:B)	1000-grain wt (g)	Aroma
					Length (mm)	Breadth (mm)			
Control	152	156	8	24	6.0	2.2	2.7	13.0	Present
CNM-RDP-42	120	100	8	16	5.5	2.8	2.0	12.5	Present
CNM-RDP-39	118	134	9	26	7.4	2.7	2.7	18.1	Present
CNM-RDP-41	136	133	6	24	7.2	2.5	2.9	16.0	Absent
CNM-RDP-46	124	19	7	20	7.8	2.5	3.1	16.5	Absent
CNM-RDP-48	139	133	6	24	7.5	2.5	3.0	16.5	Absent
CNM-RDP-35	134	100	7	21	8.8	3.0	2.6	22.3	Present
CNM-RDP-36	119	85	9	23	9.5	2.8	3.3	25.1	Absent
CNM-RDP-38	124	114	8	26	8.9	2.8	3.1	22.4	Absent
CNM-RDP-37	123	134	10	24	9.5	2.7	3.4	19.8	Present
CNM-RDP-40	120	110	9	26	8.9	2.1	4.2	15.1	Absent
CNM-RDP-43	120	103	8	26	9.3	2.0	4.5	17.6	Absent
CNM-RDP-49	137	138	6	26	9.2	2.1	4.3	17.0	Absent
CNM-RDP-50	127	81	11	21	8.9	2.2	3.9	17.5	Present

Randhuniपाल seeds to EMS at 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, and 1% concentrations for 24 h to cause mutation and develop a dwarf, aromatic, long-slender grained line, and to quantify optimum EMS dosage for this purpose.

The M₁ was grown in 1977 kharif and the M₂ in 1978. Mutation rate was

highest at 0.25% concentration, followed by 0.50%. None of the M₁ produced seeds at EMS concentrations higher than 0.50%. This may be caused by mutagenic effects at higher doses that involve many genes and lead to spikelet sterility and plant death.

Morphological and grain type mutants

were studied in the M₂. All mutants matured earlier than the control. Plant height, panicle number and length, grain size and shape, and grain weight differed substantially from those of the control (see table). Some nonaromatic mutants were obtained. Largest variation was in grain shape and weight. *ℒ*

IR36 for rainfed conditions in Madhya Pradesh, India

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IR36 is a semidwarf rice with long, slender, translucent grains and good

cooking quality. It matures in 120 d and is tolerant of gall midge and bacterial leaf blight.

In Madhya Pradesh, 80% of rice is grown in rainfed fields. IR36 performed well in multilocation tests (see table), and has become popular in areas where rainfall begins the 3d wk of Jun and continues through mid-Sep. *ℒ*

Promising new rice varieties for late kharif in the Cauvery Command Area, Karnataka, India

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Low temperatures during reproductive phase and stem borer incidence limit late kharif (Sep) rice in the Cauvery Command Area. In 1983, the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project at Mandya identified several short-duration, high yielding, stem borer

Grain yield of IR36 in rainfed areas of Madhya Pradesh.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)						Mean
	Raipur	Jabalpur	Waraseoni	Bagwai	Rewa	Jagdulpur	
<i>1978</i>							
IR36	4.3	4.0	5.4*	4.2*	6.2*	-	4.8
Rasi	3.4	3.7	4.5	3.4	4.9	-	4.0
Ratna	3.5	3.8	4.5	3.8	4.9	-	4.1
<i>1980</i>							
IR36	0.6	2.4	4.1*	-	3.8	-	2.7
Abha	0.9	2.2	3.3	-	3.3	-	2.5
<i>1982</i>							
IR36	3.2	3.4	3.7	3.7	2.3	5.0	3.5
Anupama	2.9	3.7	3.5	4.0	3.4	4.7	3.7
<i>1983</i>							
IR36	2.9*	2.1	-	2.9	3.1*	-	-
Anupama	3.0	3.1	-	2.1	2.7	-	-
Deepti	2.1	2.8	-	3.1	2.6	-	-

^a The asterisk (*) means that IR36 was superior to Ratna in 1978, to Abha in 1980, and to Deepti in 1983.

Performance of stem borer-resistant, late kharif varieties, Karnataka, India.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)	Whiteheads (%)
IET7633	109	3.2	10
IET7614	102	3.0	7
IET7261	102	2.8	8
IET7617	85	1.4	30
Mangala	94	2.3	18
CD (0.05)	-	11.7	7